

Next generation of life Saving appliances and systems for saFE and swift evacuation operations on high capacity PASSenger ships in extreme scenarios and conditions

MG-2-2-2018 Marine Accident Response No. 815146

D9.1 SafePASS Dissemination and Communication Plan

Deliverable number:	D9.1
Deliverable title:	SafePASS Dissemination and Communication Plan
Nature:	R [Document]
Dissemination Level:	PU [Public]
Author, Institution:	Fotios Stefanidis, University of Strathclyde-Maritime Safety Research Centre (MSRC)
Editor, Institution:	Dr. Evangelos Boulougouris, University of Strathclyde- Maritime Safety Research Centre (MSRC)
Leading partner:	University of Strathclyde, Maritime Safety Research Centre (MSRC)
Participating partners:	NTUA, EXUS, MSRC, TEL, DCI, DXT, TCD, SURV, CdA, RINA, RINA_S, SEAB, RCCL, DNV GL, VIK
Official submission date:	31st December 2019
Actual submission date:	31st December 2019

Modification Index			
Date	Version	Description	Edited by
19/12/2019	0.1	Draft Version - Submitted for Review	Fotios Stefanidis
20/12/2019	0.2	Review comments by TCD	Paul Liston
23/12/2019	0.3	Review comments by NTUA	Sophia Adam
24/12/2019	9.4	Review comments by SEAB	Eleni Krikigianni
30/12/2019	0.5	Incorporation of review comments	Fotios Stefanidis
31/12/2019	1.0	Final version by coordinator	Lazaros Karagiannidis

This work is a part of the SafePASS project. SafePASS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 815146.

Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Acronyms and Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
PO	Project Officer
IMO	International Maritime Organisation
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens (<i>Coordinator</i>)
EXUS	EXUS Software Ltd
MSRC	University of Strathclyde
TEL	TELESTO
CDI	Crowd Dynamics International Limited
DXT	DIGINEXT
TCD	Trinity College Dublin
SURV	Survitec
CdA	Chantiers de l'Atlantique
RINA	RINA Hellas Ltd
SEAB	SEABILITY (Cyprus) Ltd
RCCL	Royal Caribbean Cruise Line
DNV GL	DNV GL
RINA_S	RINA Services S.p.A.
VIK	VIKING Life-saving Equipment
WP	Work-package
SafePASS	Next generation of life Saving appliances and systems for saFE and swift evacuation operations on high capacity PASSenger ships in extreme scenarios and conditions
INEA	Innovation and Networks Executive Agency
GA	Grant Agreement
COP	Common Operational Picture
LSAs	Life-saving Appliances

PSE	Personal Survival Equipment
COMP	Completed
TBA	To be Announced
TBD	To be Determined
OA	Open Access
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PMs	Person Months

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1 Purpose & scope of the Document.....	9
1.2 Intended Readership	10
1.3 Central Definitions	10
1.4 Associated SafePASS Deliverables.....	11
1.4.1 SafePASS Work-packages.....	12
2. Communication and Scientific Dissemination Strategy.....	12
2.1 Awareness Raising Phases	12
2.2 Approach.....	13
2.2.1 SafePASS Key Messages	17
3. Brand Identity and Templates	18
3.1 Brand Identity and Guidelines of use	18
3.1.1 SafePASS Logo.....	18
3.1.2 Colour Palette	20
3.2 Templates.....	20
4. Communication and Dissemination Tools and Channels	21
4.1 Newsletters	22
4.2 Press Releases and Media Coverage.....	22
4.3 Information Material	24
4.4 Scientific Dissemination and Event Participation	25
4.4.1 Scientific Publication.....	25
4.4.2 Conferences, Exhibitions and Workshops	26
4.5 Video Introducing Outputs	27
4.6 Website	28
4.7 Social Media	28
4.8 Project Presentations at University Courses	31
5. Monitoring and Assessment of KPIs	32
6. Implementation	33
6.1 Work Effort per Partner	33
6.2 Dissemination Procedures	33
6.2.1 Description and Purpose.....	34
6.2.2 Dissemination Board.....	34

6.2.3 Basic Objectives	34
6.2.4 Dissemination Activity Approval Process.....	34
6.2.5 Non- European Travel	36
6.2.6 Acknowledgement on EU funding	36
7. Concluding Remarks.....	37
REFERENCES	38
ANNEXES	39
Annex 1: SafePASS 1 st Press Release – Kick off meeting	40
Annex 2: Dissemination and Communication Opportunities Tables.....	43
Annex 3: Dissemination Procedures Template Tables	45

List of Figures

Figure 1: Timeline of Dissemination & Communication Related Deliverables.....	11
Figure 2: Awareness Raising Phases.....	13
Figure 3: SafePASS Stakeholder Groups.....	16
Figure 4: SafePASS Logo- Positive.....	19
Figure 5: SafePASS Logo- Negative.....	19
Figure 6: SafePASS Icon.....	19
Figure 7: Examples of Improper Use SafePASS Logo.....	20
Figure 8: SafePASS Primary Colour Palette.....	20
Figure 9: SafePASS Secondary Colour Palette.....	20
Figure 10: SafePASS ResearchGate Page.....	26
Figure 11: SafePASS Youtube Channel.....	27
Figure 12: SafePASS Website.....	28
Figure 13: SafePASS LinkedIn Page.....	30
Figure 15: SafePASS Twitter Page.....	31
Figure 14: SafePASS Facebook Page.....	31

List of Table

Table 1: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Differences [3].....	10
Table 2: List of SafePASS Work-packages, Leading Partners and Duration.....	12
Table 3: Targeted Stakeholders.....	14
Table 3: EC Mass Media Opportunities for Dissemination of News [4].....	23
Table 4: Provisional Plan for Newsletters and Press Releases Error! Bookmark not defined.	
Table 5: Provisional Deadlines for the creation of the Information Material.....	25
Table 6: EC Research and Innovation Events and Scientific Publishing Opportunities [4].....	26
Table 7: EC Research and Innovation Events and Scientific Publishing Opportunities [4]. Error! Bookmark not defined.	
Table 8: Planned Workshops.....	27
Table 9: Activities, Actions and Success Metrics.....	32
Table 10: WP9 Work Effort Distribution and PMs per Partner.....	33
Table 11: Calendar of Dissemination Opportunity Events.....	43
Table 12: List of Scientific Journals for SafePASS papers.....	44
Table 13: Dissemination Activity Request Table.....	45
Table 14: Dissemination Activities Registry- Conferences.....	45
Table 15: Dissemination Activities Registry- Technical Papers.....	46
Table 16: Dissemination Activities Registry- Journal Papers.....	46
Table 17: Dissemination Activities Registry- Project Events.....	47
Table 18: Dissemination Activities Registry- Other Dissemination Activities.....	47
Table 19: Dissemination Activities Registry- Mass Media Presence.....	48

Executive Summary

This document constitutes the **Dissemination and Communication Plan**, the first deliverable (**D9.1**) of **WP9- Communication and Impact booster** of the SafePASS project as set out in Grant Agreement (GA) No. 815146 between the project's partners and INEA [1].

Its purpose is to outline the strategy for the management and monitoring of the dissemination and communication activities of the project. In more detail (i) it lays down the communication and scientific dissemination strategy (ii) it presents the communication and dissemination tools (iii) the monitoring and assessment process (iv) the implementation plan and the dissemination procedures. As such, it will leverage the progressive awareness of the project's outputs and their impact among all stakeholders and the general public. Furthermore, it will ensure alignment with the Annotated Model GA Articles 29 & 38 and it will serve as a reference point for the consortium members for any related actions.

1. Introduction

The first section of this chapter outlines the purpose and scope of the document, the intended readership and identifies the interrelation of this deliverable with other project deliverables. Moreover, in the same section, the terms: ‘Communication’ and ‘Dissemination’ are being defined and their main differences are being clarified.

Section 2 outlines the communication and scientific dissemination strategy. In section 3, the brand identity is presented, while section 4 describes the communication and dissemination tools and channels. Section 5 presents the KPIs and the monitoring process while section 6 summarized the dissemination guidelines and implementation process of the activities.

1.1 Purpose & scope of the Document

The purpose of this document is to set a strategy for the management and monitoring of the dissemination and communication activities of the project with the aim to gradually raise awareness of the project’s outputs and their impact, both amongst the immediate stakeholders and specifically targeted communities but also among the general public. The communication and dissemination plan outlined herein will ensure adherence to the Annotated Model GA Articles 29 & 38 [2] and be a reference point for the consortium members for any related action.

More specifically, this document is dedicated to the:

- Identification of the Dissemination Targets.
- Development of the dissemination and communication strategies, activities and media channels, for achieving a higher outreach for the project and facilitating its exploitation activities.
- Assignment of tasks and responsibilities to the partners involved.

The dissemination and communication strategies/ activities should be constantly monitored, reviewed and potentially adjusted, throughout the course of the project, in order to ensure the maximum effectiveness in the visibility and exploitation of the project’s outputs. Any deviation from the strategies, activities or procedures set by this document will be reported and justified in the Dissemination Activity Reports (deliverables No. D.9.2.x).

What this document is NOT

This document is not intended as a comprehensive dissemination activity report. Dissemination Activity Reports will instead be published annually (First- M12, Interim- M24, Final- M36)¹ and include substantial information for the various communication and dissemination activities undertaken up to that particular year.

¹ August 2020/2021/20222

1.2 Intended Readership

This document is primarily written for the European Commission (EC) Project Officer (PO) and the consortium members of the SafePASS Project.

Nevertheless, since the dissemination level of this document has been set as ‘Public’ (PU), special effort and attention has been given in making this report as a stand-alone document and comprehensible for the general public.

1.3 Central Definitions

In order to avoid misconceptions, this section is providing the definitions of the most fundamental terms in an attempt to create successful and targeted action plans. The following definitions are given, based on the European’s IPR Helpdesk [3] and the EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms.

Communication: Actions that make the research activities known to multiple audiences (in a way that they can be understood by non-specialists) and the activities must address the public policy perspective of EU research and innovation funding, by considering aspects such as (i) transnational cooperation in a European consortium (i.e. how working together has allowed to achieve more than otherwise possible) or (ii) scientific excellence or (iii) contributing to competitiveness and to solving societal challenges.

Dissemination: It refers, specifically for the H2020 programme, to the means of public disclosure of the results (other than protecting or exploiting them, e.g. scientific publications).

Exploitation: It refers, specifically for the H2020 programme, to the means that make use of the results produced in an EU project in further activities (other than those covered by the project, e.g. in developing, creating and marketing a product, process or service).

Audience: Different groups of people to whom the communication activities are targeted for and whose interest we seek to engage (e.g. general public, EU citizens).

Stakeholders: Groups or individuals who are either directly interested in the project or who can be directly impacted by the project’s outputs (e.g. Cruise ship ow companies, Life-Saving Appliances manufacturers, IMO regulators).

The table below summarises the differences the differences in objectives, focus and target audiences as these arise by the aforementioned definitions.

Table 1: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Differences [3]

	Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
Objectives	Show to the society the Impact and	Transfer Knowledge and Results	Effectively Use Project Results

	Benefits of EU-funded R&I activities		
Focus	Inform and Promote the Project and its Results	Describe and Ensure Results are Available for others to Use	Make Use of the Results
Target Audience	Multiple Audiences, broad public	Audiences that can make use of the results	Any people/organisations that can make use of the results
Formal Obligations	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Rules for Participants GA Art. 38.1 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Rules for Participants GA Art. 29 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Rules for Participants GA Art. 28

1.4 Associated SafePASS Deliverables

The Dissemination and Communication Plan is closely linked with the following deliverables, all of which will be publicly available:

D9.2.x: SafePASS annual dissemination and communication activity reports. First/Interim/Final report on dissemination and communication activities undertaken by the project for each year.

D9.3.x: SafePASS Business Plan: First/Final version of report on business plan for the exploitation of the SafePASS results.

D9.4: IMO recommendations report. Report on the analysis of proposed amendments to IMO regulations.

Figure 1: Timeline of Dissemination & Communication Related Deliverables

1.4.1 SafePASS Work-packages

Table 2: List of SafePASS Work-packages, Leading Partners and Duration

WP No.	WP Title	Leading Partner	Start-End
1	Project Management	NTUA	M01-M36
2	SafePASS Design, User & System Requirements	NTUA	M01-M24
3	SafePASS next generation lifesaving appliances and adaptation to novel ship architectural structures	SURV	M04-M29
4	SafePASS Smart Environment	TEL	M05-M29
5	SafePASS core platform	EXUS	M05-M29
6	Risk modelling and cost-benefit analysis	MSRC	M03-M33
7	Evidence Based assessment & Socio-technical Modelling	TCD	M01-M36
8	SafePASS Integration, experimentation and pilot demonstrations	EXUS	M13-M36
9	Communication and Impact booster	MSRC	M01-M36
10	Ethics Requirements	NTUA	M01-M36

2. Communication and Scientific Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Awareness Raising Phases

The awareness raising strategy of SafePASS consists of three phases, each pertaining to different stages of the project and thus each one has a different set of goals.

Phase 1: Preliminary Project Promotion

The first phase is focused on the definition and implementation of the communication strategy and to the creation of a plan for future Activities. Its aim is to create the first base of project followers by promoting the project's vision, objectives and progress. During Phase 1, the dissemination and communication activities are generic enough to allow for a wide range of demographics to gain interest to the project. This phase refers mainly to the first year of the project and will be refined and updated throughout the whole life cycle of the project.

Phase 2: Project Commercialisation

The second phase is essentially a refined iteration of the first phase but with a focus to more targeted audiences. During this phase, the focus of communication and dissemination activities will be on the technologies, systems and solutions that have been developed within SafePASS. The main target groups of that phase are the key stakeholders. This phase refers mainly to the second and third year of the project.

Phase 3: Business Strategy

The final phase will be dedicated to the promotion of the benefits/impact associated with the project's outputs. The aim is to inform the industry and academia about potential exploitation opportunities and, through the exploitation of such opportunities, to achieve sustainability. This phase refers mainly to the third year of the project.

Figure 2: Awareness Raising Phases

2.2 Approach

The SafePASS approach to communication and dissemination follows a four-step methodology, which is presented below and intends to increase the impact of dissemination and communication actions. It is based on four questions that have to be considered when planning or undergoing a communication or dissemination activity.

Step 1: Why communicate and disseminate?

The high visibility of the project and the promotion of active interaction with key stakeholders (Step 3 “To whom to communicate and disseminate?”) are elements of accountability that will enable ship industry to understand why it is worth investing money in order to support this Research and Innovation Action. In other words, it is highly important to deliver the highest possible impact to stakeholders outside the project partnership and ensure that:

- (i) Project outputs can be fully exploited and be used in the most effective manner, i.e. the scaling-up of the demonstrated solutions is facilitated;

- (ii) (ii) Knowledge gained through the project, and more generally the information generated by the project, can be made available to all interested organisations;
- (iii) (iii) Elements of excellence of the project can be reused and replicated in other projects, becoming a reference point triggering further developments in the field and beyond;
- (iv) (iv) Project reaches decision-makers to contribute improving future policies;
- (v) (v) Benefits that project outcomes will bring to society (services, employment, economy) are well pointed out.

Step 2: What to communicate and to disseminate?

The following project information will be communicated to the relevant audience:

- (i) Vision (objectives, strategic relevance) and key facts: messages will follow an evolution from the start of the project to the aftermath and therefore, they will be reviewed periodically in the course of the project. A description of SafePASS key messages and relevant vision and objectives is presented in section 2.2.1;
- (ii) News (achievements and results): experiences will illustrate the impact of the project and will give a human dimension that can catalyse end-users' acceptance;
- (iii) Events promotion and events results.

The following project outputs will be disseminated as widely as possible: (i) Ready for use SafePASS System and individual technologies, along with lessons-learned and user guidelines; (ii) Recommendations to IMO and other regulatory and standardization bodies.

Step 3: To whom to communicate and to disseminate?

Key stakeholders of the SafePASS target audience have been initially organized into several categories and are presented below.

Table 3: Targeted Stakeholders

Industrial	End-users	Facilitators
ICT Solution Developers	IMO	EU Institutions
LSA Manufacturers	Ship Building Industries	Classification Societies
Software and Application Developers	Ship Operators	National Public Authorities

Industrial	End-users	Facilitators
Scientific Community		Related EU-funded Projects
Ship Industries		Public Bodies & Environmental Organisations
Cruise Operators		IMO
		European Policy Makers (MEPs)

A comprehensive stakeholder analysis will be conducted as part of WP2 and T2.2 “Mission and operational requirements”, which will facilitate the implementation and execution of targeted dissemination and communication activities. This analysis will further cluster the different stakeholder into primary and secondary stakeholders and will exploit the internal SafePASS stakeholders and their links, business and/or communication channels to industrial stakeholders, end-users and facilitators.

According to the degree stakeholders are affected by the SafePASS project, we identify two types of stakeholders:

- Primary stakeholders: stand to be directly affected by the project, decisions or actions of the project
- Secondary stakeholders: are indirectly affected by the project or decision or actions of the project

Cruise lines’ stakeholders can be defined as any individual or group of physical or juridical persons holding a legitimate interest, or being affected, by cruise lines’ actions or inactions^{2,3}. Such potential stakeholders are numerous and may be clustered into different categories. Figure 3 visualizes the most important cruise stakeholder groups, i.e., shareholders, creditors, managers and employees (internal stakeholders) and customers/cruisers, port authorities, terminal operators, local community/environment, regulators, suppliers (external stakeholders).

The light blue color indicates the identified primary SafePASS project stakeholders, while the light yellow color indicates the secondary stakeholders.

² Satta, G.; Parola, F.; Penco, L.; Persico, L. Cruise lines searching for legitimacy: Stakeholder relationship management and CSR reporting. In Proceedings of the International Association of Maritime Economists Conference, Kyoto, Japan, 27–30 June 2017

³ Lester, J.-A.; Weeden, C. Stakeholders, the natural environment and the future of Caribbean cruise tourism. *Int. J. Tour. Res.* 2004, 6, 39–50.

Figure 3: SafePASS Stakeholder Groups

Besides the project's stakeholder groups, SafePASS will be disseminated to the general public and press.

Step 4: How to communicate and to disseminate?

The dissemination activities will be carried out in three directions:

- (i) **Awareness:** The goal of this direction will be to make the project and its vision known in the relevant target groups. Primary instruments will be the partnering end users, the project website and newsletter, the project presence in social networks, the participation to relevant conferences, events and workshops as well as gaining positive coverage in the media via press releases and other press activities.
- (ii) **Scientific and technological achievements:** The second direction focuses on the scientific and technological results of the project. Primary instruments will be the presentation of research articles and technical demonstrations at conferences and journals, as well as building up a community of interested developers and scientists.
- (iii) **Demonstrators:** The third direction is dedicated to promote SafePASS to the Shipping ecosystem through dedicated workshops and open demonstrations (T7.3 and T8.6). The goal is to make the target groups aware of the benefits provided by the SafePASS concept.

In addition, clustering and liaising activities with other relevant RDI projects and European initiatives will run horizontally through the three dissemination and communication activity directions. The main liaising activities will target:

- Awareness raising of relevant RDI projects through web presence and social media channels
- Invitation and/or co-organization of dissemination and communication events, workshops and open demonstration events with relevant RDI projects and EU initiatives

2.2.1 SafePASS Key Messages

To summarize the project's key messages that will be disseminated and communicated to the various stakeholder groups, a brief introduction of SafePASS, its vision and objectives, are presented in this section.

2.2.1.1 SafePASS at a Glance

Maritime accidents such as the grounding of MS Costa Concordia in 2012, the fire onboard MS Norman Atlantic in 2014 and more recently the incident with the MS Viking Sky vessel, create societal pressure for improving safety in the maritime sector, but more importantly they serve to highlight gaps in existing procedures, constraints in the capabilities of the existing life-saving appliances and the overall effectiveness of current procedures and response to the risks posed by the evacuation process itself.

The challenge, therefore, lies in the development of cost-effective solutions that will indeed reduce loss of life in case of an evacuation, regardless of the demographical characteristics of the passengers or the environmental conditions at the location of the accident.

To address this issue, it crucial to learn from experience, pursue international joint research initiatives that can lead to more widely agreed positions in the problem, and invest in engineering and research innovations.

2.2.1.2 The Goal

SafePASS aims to radically redefine the evacuation processes, evacuation systems/equipment and international regulations for passenger ships in all environments, hazards and weather conditions, independently of the demographic factor, by developing an integrated system that will collectively monitor, process and inform during emergencies both crew and passengers of the optimal evacuation routes, coupled with advanced, intuitive and easy to use LSA, resulting as such to a significant reduction of the total time required for ship evacuation and increased safety.

2.2.1.3 The Objectives

O1: Develop a comprehensive post-incident approach from ALARM to RESCUE, including mustering and abandonment in pertinent extreme flooding and fire scenarios, leading to risk estimation and impact of appropriate risk control measures post-flooding/fire emergencies.

O2: Design and develop next generation life-saving appliances for large capacity passenger ships.

O3: Design and develop advanced evacuation support tools and methods that will radically improve evacuation operations while enhancing situation awareness on board.

O4: Introduce an advanced platform which addresses the safety needs of passengers during complex evacuation processes by identifying, designating and sustaining a Location-based Dynamic Evacuation Route that adapts according to current and evolving circumstances and guides passengers, while facilitating crew coordination.

O5: Provide social- and behavioural-driven solutions compatible with international legislation, standards & regulations (SOLAS, GDPR, etc.) and recommendations for future adoption.

O6: Validate and demonstrate SafePASS developments on industrially relevant environment.

3. Brand Identity and Templates

3.1 Brand Identity and Guidelines of use

The brand identity of the project was developed after several iterations, considering the feedback from the partners on multiple logo versions. The brand identity was defined so as to capture the interest of the viewers while also demonstrating the marine and evacuation related aspect of the project.

Guidelines on the use of the logo, the proposed colour palettes and typographical font options have been produced and are available for the consortium in the project's document repository tool Redmine. Please refer to the guidelines for the proper use of the logo in different backgrounds and be informed about the improper use of logo.

The partners can download the logo and icon files from Redmine. The logo files are being provided in different file types (.png and .pdf) and resolutions to cover as much of wide range of use as possible. This material can be also downloaded for interested audiences through the project website, in the download area of dissemination material.

3.1.1 SafePASS Logo

The logo of the project is composed by the following principal components:

- The body plan view of a ship, having its bottom part trimmed in a 'wave' like manner. This is a clear reference to the marine related nature of the project.
- The two arrows extending from the deck height and point out of the vessel thus suggesting a movement out of the ship. A minimalistic reference to evacuation.
- The label with the name of the project 'SafePASS', implying the safety related endeavours of the project.

Figure 4: SafePASS Logo- Positive

Figure 5: SafePASS Logo- Negative

3.1.1.1 Icon

A simplified version of the logo was also created for the use as profile picture in the social media accounts. The icon is essentially a version of the logo without the label part.

Figure 6: SafePASS Icon

3.1.1.2 Improper Use

Do not rotate, skew, redraw, scale, redraw, reproduce, alter, or otherwise distort the SafePASS logo in any way.

Do not combine the SafePASS logo with any other element such as other logos, graphics, words, photos, slogans, or symbols.

Figure 7: Examples of Improper Use SafePASS Logo

3.1.2 Colour Palette

Standardising the set of colours that can be used together with the project’s logo safeguards the visual consistency of the project’s brand identity and increases its effectiveness. The colour palette was developed to match the colours of the logo and determines the colour aesthetics of current and future dissemination and communication tools such as the website, leaflets, brochures, posters etc.

Figure 8: SafePASS Primary Colour Palette

Figure 9: SafePASS Secondary Colour Palette

3.2 Templates

The templates used for the various documentations needs of the project have to be in line with the project’s visual identity and make use of the aforementioned colour palette.

Up to this point the following templates have been designed and are available for use to all the consortium members via the project’s document repository Redmine:

1. SafePASS Agenda Template (.docx)

2. SafePASS Minutes of Meeting Template (.docx)
3. SafePASS Deliverable Template (.docx)
4. SafePASS Letter Template (.docx)
5. SafePASS Presentation Template (.pptx)
6. SafePASS Project- Non-European Travel Report Template (.docx)
7. SafePASS Registration List Template (.docx)

Templates for other types of documents will be created if needed and will be available for the partners via the project's document repository tool Redmine.

4. Communication and Dissemination Tools and Channels

For an effective messaging, a broad range of communication channels including traditional and new media will be utilized by the project to reach, speak and interact with its target audiences, capturing their attention frequently and precisely.

The main communication and dissemination channels used to target specific groups of stakeholders have been divided into one-way channels and two-way channels. One-way channels have the benefit of achieving broad visibility, reaching the general public and masses and enjoying the credibility of established media platforms. Two-way channels can be seen as more effective as they involve dialogue, interactivity and flexibility, but they often reach a smaller number of people. The key communication channels for SafePASS are detailed below.

(i) One Way Communication channels for SafePASS

- Project website
- Digital media, such as online newspapers and magazines
- Traditional media, such as TV, radio and press
- Communication and dissemination materials, such as roll up banners, leaflets, factsheets and promo videos
- Newsletters
- Press releases, Advertorials
- Journal publications
- Papers in technical conferences

(ii) Two Way Communication channels for SafePASS

- Social media: Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook; Interactive discussion on social media
- Dialogue with networks, communities and associations
- Participation in field events such as conferences, fairs and workshops

- Conference booths
- Pilots
- Workshops
- Open Event
- Project presentations at university courses

The following sections list and analyze the key Communication and Dissemination tools and channels.

4.1 Newsletters

The creation and distribution of newsletters is one of the communication tools that is going to be employed for the dissemination of important news about the project such as the presentation of outputs and their impact, the participation of project delegates in conferences and exhibitions and any forthcoming events. It has been agreed that throughout the course of the project there will be at least nine newsletters.

With regards to the distribution of the newsletters, all the available means will be utilised in order to reach the highest possible readership. More specifically the newsletters will be uploaded in the project's website, Facebook and LinkedIn pages, links directing to the publication will be posted in SafePASS' twitter account and e-mails will be sent to SafePASS' Stakeholder database. In addition, members of the consortium will be asked to forward the newsletter to their colleagues and use their institution's/ company's communication tools to further spread the project's news to their own networks.

Table 4: Provisional Plan for Newsletters

Newsletter								
Month	M09	M15	M20	M23	M38	M32	M35	M36
Status	TBA	TBA	TBA	TBA	TBA	TBA	TBA	TBA
Content	1 st Stakeholder Workshop Results	TBD						

4.2 Press Releases and Media Coverage

Gaining positive coverage in the media is amongst the main goals of SafePASS and is expected to have an incredible impact on the work we do. Getting more people thinking positively about the project and spreading its messages across to a wider

audience are key prerequisites for SafePASS' communication and dissemination activities and a great way of providing the project and its assets with greater credibility.

Project's press releases will be developed by MSRC for all major events and in order to disseminate the project's key findings and results in various trusted local and European media. Partners will be responsible for translations and regional adaptations as well as to create media contact lists with key journalists and bloggers specialised in maritime section, technology and science.

Additionally, more media activities such as interviews, exclusive stories and editorials, designed to look and read like informative articles on SafePASS, will be planned for publications in the popular and subject press, being extra powerful tools for gaining valuable publicity and boost project's visibility.

The consortium members will be also advised by MSRC to make use of EU's mass media platforms to promote the projects news. A list of these potentially useful tools can be found in the table below but for more information please refer to the dedicated EU document 'Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants' [4].

Table 5: EC Mass Media Opportunities for Dissemination of News [4]

Mass Media	Description/Information
Horizon Magazine	Publication- EU Research and Innovation e- magazine. Updated 3 times a week with new articles. email: publications@ec.europa.eu
Project Stories	Articles about interesting exploited outputs, discoveries and breakthroughs based on EU-funded research projects. Contact: PO
Research* EU Results Magazine	Features highlights from EU-funded projects. Published 10 times per year. Contact: PO
Research* EU Focus	This print magazine covers in each issue a specific topic of research interest. Contact: PO
CORDIS Wire	CORDIS Wire provides registered users with a simple interface to publish articles on the CORDIS website's News and Events service. All articles are moderated by CORDIS editors before publication.
Headlines	Headlines report on recent developments in research and innovation in Europe and beyond and are devoted purely to projects. Suitable stories to be published on the site are

	selected on a daily basis. It is connected to the CORDIS Wire.
--	--

The publication of the 1st press release has already been completed and a copy of it can be found in the Appendix 1. A version of the Press Release is also available in Greek⁴. The final versions of Press Releases and Newsletters will be available for download to the consortium members via the project's document repository Redmine and to the public via the SafePASS website.

Local Media Presence: During SafePASS, all partners will disseminate non-confidential information of the project in their national language to local/regional newspapers and media.

4.3 Information Material

Other types of on-way communication tools to be employed are leaflets, brochures, posters and roll-up banners. This information material will be consistent with the brand identity of the project and will convey the information about the vision and objectives and impact of SafePASS. They should also direct their intended targets to the project's social media accounts. In more detail:

SafePASS factsheet: will be a short description of the project the consortium partners and the GA and funding information.

SafePASS brochure/leaflet: will provide an overview of the project's vision, the SafePASS ecosystems and the expected impact. The main objective of this tool is to be distributed during SafePASS activities such as workshops, events, conferences and exhibitions. Depending on the target audience, it may be enriched technical tailored details and illustrations on the SafePASS ecosystem and subsystems.

SafePASS self-standing roll-up banner: will act as an important resource for SafePASS, accommodating the fact that "an advert seen once by a million people will not be as effective as an advert seen four times by a quarter of a million people". It will be developed, for disseminating the project outcomes at specific events, such as exterior workshops, conferences, exhibitions and at the SafePASS Final Event.

SafePASS poster: will mainly serve the scientific dissemination activities of the project, towards providing more technical details of the SafePASS ecosystem in relevant technical and scientific conferences.

The information material, once prepared, will be created according to the plan below and will be available for printing to all partners via a dedicated folder in the project's document repository tool Redmine. All partners are encouraged to have with them and distribute this information material when participating in conferences or other dissemination or communication activities. For interested audiences this material will be also available in the project's website download area.

⁴ <http://www.ictplus.gr/default.asp?pid=30&rID=63989&ct=8&la=1>

Table 6: Provisional Deadlines for the creation of the Information Material

Information Material				
Information Material	Fact Sheet	Brochure/Leaflet	Poster	Roll-up Banner
Month	M07	M07	M08	M08
Content	SafePASS Vision, Objectives and Ecosystems			
Information Material	Leaflet		Poster	
Month	M30		M30	
Content	SafePASS Outputs and Impact			

4.4 Scientific Dissemination and Event Participation

4.4.1 Scientific Publication

One of the core research outputs of the project will be the free access publications in the form of journal/conference papers as well as whitepapers. This form of dissemination will be targeting specifically scientific and industrial stakeholders. The dissemination procedures and that have to be followed by the members of the consortium are outlined in Chapter 6.2 of this document and are meant to assess the quality of the dissemination actions.

All partners have been provided with a link for Google sheet where they can add any Scientific Journals that might be of interest for paper publications and are invited to populate this throughout the course of the project. The same Google sheets has a separate tab with a table listing potentially useful events such as exhibitions and conferences. Examples of these tables, showing the type of information that the members of the consortium are invited to add, can be found in the Annex 2.

The EC is also organising some Research and Innovation events and provides an electronic gateway for scientific journals, something which SafePASS consortium intends to exploit.

Table 7: EC Research and Innovation Events and Scientific Publishing Opportunities [4]

Access Point	Description/Information
Events on the EC’s Research and Innovation website	An event can be suggested by using the “Suggest an event” functionality which is available on the right-hand side of the website.
Events on the CORDIS website	This website displays research-related conferences and events
Openaire	An electronic gateway for open access peer-reviewed papers and other important publications (e.g. conference publications)

The publication of scientific papers is a task which is expected to be carried out primarily by the academic partners of SafePASS, namely NTUA, MSRC and TCD. Attention should be given to the ‘underlying principle’ of Open Access (OA) with regards any scientific publications and research data have been produced within the context of the SafePASS Project [5]. Consortium members are requested to become familiar with the official Guidelines of EU-funded projects regarding OA by referring to the following material provided by the EC:

1. [Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020](#)
2. [Webinar on Open Access to Publications in Horizon 2020](#)
3. [Webinars: H2020 policies on Open Access and Research Data](#)

The project’s publications can also be posted in the social networking site for scientists and researchers ResearchGate in order to increase awareness within those communities. The academic partners are invited to use their institution’s email to register in ResearchGate and become members of the SafePASS – H2020 Project ([link](#)).

Figure 10: SafePASS ResearchGate [Page](#)

4.4.2 Conferences, Exhibitions and Workshops

The industrial partners of SafePASS will represent the project in various exhibition and conference via their company’s booths and ensure the distribution of the information material produced for such events. Moreover, SafePASS will actively participate in workshops and meetings arranged by the EC or proposed by PO. **The results of the**

project should be presented at least 2 conferences or dissemination events for the minimum dissemination goals to be met.

Each academic partner is also committed of making at least one project related presentation per year at a university course. These lectures should be addressed to students of all academic levels (undergraduate and postgraduate) and aim in not only raising awareness of the project but also increase the competitive edge of European students.

SafePASS consortium will organise at least three workshops/ open events within the framework of different WP. Each workshop will have different function and aim, serving the needs of the WP that is being related to. The definition of SafePASS Design, User and System Requirements (WP2), the design of next generation of LSAs (WP3) and the Evidence Based Assessment & Socio-technical modelling (WP7) require the active engagement/input and feedback of internal and external stakeholders and which can be achieved with workshops.

Table 8: Planned Workshops

Related WP	Short Description	Month
WP2	Stakeholder Requirements Workshop	M06
WP3	Next Generation of LSAs Requirements Workshop	M06
WP7	Initialisation of Community of Practise Workshop	M06

4.5 Video Introducing Outputs

A short-animated video is to be produced towards the end of the project which will be focused on the SafePASS systems and solutions in increasing safety during marine emergency response. The video will be uploaded in the project's Youtube channel ([link](#)) and distributed via all the communication platforms of SafePASS but also alternative Audio-visual platforms like Euronews ([link](#)).

Figure 11: SafePASS [Youtube Channel](#)

4.6 Website

All the necessary provisions (allocation of resources) have been made with regards the project's website related tasks. SafePASS website ([link⁵](#)) is the main media tool for communication and dissemination of project related material. It's modern design and aesthetics aim to spark the interest of the visitors whilst regular updates on its content and functionalities will ensure the highest possible quality and efficiency of the communication and dissemination objectives.

As of the 25th of May 2018, EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has become enforceable and acts as a mandate for clear and careful acquisition, storage and handling process of personal information. In the light of this, SafePASS partners as a whole but more importantly those who lead the Ethics Requirements (WP10), the Dissemination and Communication activities (WP9) and designing/managing the website (EXUS) should ensure adherence to the current regulations regarding the website's cookies policy or other implications rising from the GDPR.

Figure 12: SafePASS [Website](#)

The project's website will remain active for at least two years after the completion of the project and together with the project's social media accounts will continue the dissemination of the project's outputs and inform the public about the impact of SafePASS solutions and any associated exploitation actions.

4.7 Social Media

The social media accounts of the project have been active since M01 and are being updated with new content on a regular basis. The project's social media accounts will be promoting SafePASS activities and inform the public on issues that are within the thematic scope of the project. The social media accounts are managed and controlled by the dissemination manager (MSRC), including the engagement of all project partners on a regular basis. This includes the dissemination of SafePASS social media accounts and activities through the consortium partners own social media networks.

⁵ <http://www.safepass-project.eu/>

The social media account presence will spread across all target audience ranging from general public and cruise line passengers to cruise line operators, safety personnel, LSA and PSE manufacturers, classification societies, shipyards, academia and research centres, international organisations and associations, regulatory bodies, EU projects, national authorities, coast guards, maritime training centres, ICT companies and service providers. The social media tools will be used for presenting the latest news about the project with: updates and pictures from meetings, workshops and events, direct links to the project material as well as sharing news of initiatives, partners, similar projects and industry. All SafePASS consortium partners are engaged in increasing the awareness of the social media tools, by creating linkages to their accounts and by providing MSRC with relevant content and contributions related to their achievements.

The social media presence will be assessed on a regular basis including the frequency of posts, post shares and retweets, the reactions (such as likes, reposts comments, messages etc.), the increase of followers and members etc. so as to shape the strategy towards maximizing the impact of the project's social media account.

English language will be used in all social media accounts.

LinkedIn Account:

A LinkedIn page ([Link](#)) was created for the project as a platform for the engagement of the professional communities that are interested in maritime safety related topics. The community hashtags of the page (#cruiseships, #safety, #H2020) were chosen strategically so as to portrait the project's area of operation while also being generic enough to allow for exposure to a wider range of audiences.

Figure 13: SafePASS [LinkendIn Page](#)

Twitter Account:

A Twitter account ([Link](#)) is created for disseminating project news, events and results as well as maritime safety and cruise industry new and topics. The use of handles such as @EU_H2020, @consortium members handles (companies, academia, persons), hashtags and emojis is foreseen to be included in order to maximize the impact of the posts. Twitter will target mainly posting of short and clear content, including pictures and link to project website, newsletters etc. and retweets from related twitter accounts of initiatives, partners, and similar projects.

 Figure 14: SafePASS [Twitter Page](#)

Facebook Account:

A Facebook page ([Link](#)) was created for communicating mainly with the general public and showcase the project and results in an informal but highly accessible way. The Facebook page will be used in order to post project's news, photos and media files as well as interesting reports and news related to passenger safety and the cruise line market. It is foreseen to include tags of authors, projects partners, location of events etc. in order to maximize the impact of the posts.

 Figure 15: SafePASS [Facebook Page](#)

4.8 Project Presentations at University Courses

The SafePASS academic beneficiaries will disseminate the project technology developed and its application in universities. Through the academic beneficiaries

involved (MSRC, TCD, NTUA) SafePASS presentations will be given in lectures at under- and post- graduate level. These actions are envisaged to increase the knowledge and competitive edge of European students. At least 1 lecture per academic partner is foreseen

5. Monitoring and Assessment of KPIs

Measurable targets for dissemination and communication activities have been set in order to ensure that the desired impact is achieved. Table 9 describes the planned SafePASS Communication activities to be performed throughout the project course and the KPIs expected from the relevant activities.

Table 9: Activities, Actions and Success Metrics

Type of Activity	Description	KPI
Newsletters	Creation and Distribution	≥ 9
Information material	Creation of leaflets, brochures, posters	≥ 4
Whitepapers	Publications	≥ 3
Conferences/workshops/exhibitions	Participations and Organising	≥ 5
Journal Papers	Publication	≥ 8
Conference Papers	Publication	≥ 12
SafePASS workshops	Organisation of three events	3 events, ≥30 participants each
Videos introducing outputs	Production	≥ 1
Twitter	Followers	≥ 300 (≥ 100 by M24)
LinkedIn	Followers	≥ 200 (≥ 100 by M24)
Facebook	Followers	≥ 300 (≥ 100 by M24)
SafePASS Stakeholders Database	Building database	≥ 450 contacts

6. Implementation

This section describes the implementation activities of dissemination and communication with respect to the work effort per partner and the dissemination procedures.

6.1 Work Effort per Partner

The performance of communication and dissemination is directly correlated and dependent on the consistency and level of commitment of each partner. In light of this statement and according to the GA, a specific number of Person Months (PMs) have been assigned to all partners towards their contribution on the Communication and Impact Booster work-package (WP9). This binds the consortium members to actively participate in any communication and dissemination related actions and provide their input in accordance to their assigned PMs.

Table 10: WP9 Work Effort Distribution and PMs per Partner

WP9	Communication and Impact Booster							
Partner	MSRC	EXUS	NTUA	TEL	VIK	SEAB	RINA	RCCL
PMs	9	8	8	7	5	4	4	3
% of PMs	14%	12%	12%	11%	8%	6%	6%	5%
Partner	SURV	DXT	RINA_S	CdA	DNVGL	CDI	TCD	
PMs	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	
% of PMs	5%	5%	5%	3%	3%	3%	3%	

6.2 Dissemination Procedures

The Dissemination Procedures mentioned below have already been circulated to all the consortium members and uploaded to the project's online document repository tool 'Redmine'. The version of the procedures for internal use includes hyperlinks to the Google Sheet files and Redmine Folders that have to be used. These hyperlinks have been de-activated for this document for security reasons. Nevertheless, examples of the tables and the information that have to be filled are provided in the Annex 3.

6.2.1 Description and Purpose

The consortium has to adopt certain procedures for its dissemination activities. Therefore, the publication or presentation of work done within the framework of SafePASS or any other communication and dissemination activity related to the SafePASS project has to comply with the dissemination procedures outlined herein.

6.2.2 Dissemination Board

The role of the Dissemination Board is dictated by our pursuit for quality, fairness, transparency and maximization of the project's impact. The board needs to review the submissions and verify that:

- The quality is at the expected level
- The contents have proper references to the work conducted by the partners and have the proper clearance in order to avoid unintended disclosure of confidential information
- In case there are issues, the panel should be able to justify properly its decisions and provide guidance

The submissions to be reviewed will be mainly newsletters, journal papers, conference presentations etc. More details about the role of the Dissemination Board can be found in the Dissemination Activities Approval Process.

The members of the Dissemination Board are as follows:

1. MSRC ([Dr. Evangelos Boulougouris](#), [Prof. Dracos Vassalos](#))
2. NTUA (Mr. [Lazaros Karagiannidis](#), [Dr. Nikolaos Ventikos](#))
4. EXUS ([Dimitrios Katsaros](#))
5. TCD ([Dr. Paul Liston](#))

6.2.3 Basic Objectives

- Produce high quality SafePASS publications, presentations and other types of communication material;
- Avoid overlaps and potential disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Monitoring and recording of the dissemination activities of the project in an effective and efficient way.

6.2.4 Dissemination Activity Approval Process

Any publication or presentation of work done within the framework of SafePASS or any other communication and dissemination activity related to the SafePASS project has to be approved beforehand by the SafePASS Project Coordinator and the Dissemination Board.

6.2.4.1 Step-by-step procedures

1. At least two weeks before the publisher's or organizer's deadline for submission of a paper or proposal for presentation, the initiator of the dissemination activity must:
 - Register the planned activity to the *Dissemination Activity Request Table* (see example on Annex) Google Sheets file by adding a new row at the end of the list and filling the columns.
 - Store the file for review in the Redmine folder *Documents for Review*.
 - Inform via email, with subject: "SafePASS – Dissemination Request", the WP9 Leader (Dr. Evangelos Boulougouris, MSRC).
2. The WP9 Leader has then two days to forward the request to the Dissemination Board for approval, modification or rejection.
3. The Dissemination Board members have to reply to the WP9 Leader within 5 working days; no response is considered as approval.
4. The WP9 Leader informs the initiator and the WP9 Leader about the decision. In case of:
 - Approval: The partner(s) involved in the dissemination activity may proceed with the submission and realization of the activity;
 - Conflict/Objection: Any member of the Dissemination Board can object the proposed dissemination activity; for example in case of disclosure of restricted or confidential information. In such an event, the WP9 Leader informs the partner of any required modifications or additions. Then the material is proposed again to WP9 Leader and if were made significant changes that might raise conflicts among the partner's interests, the previous procedure is repeated.
5. Within 10 working days after the realization of the approved dissemination activity, the initiator of the dissemination activity must:
 - i. Update the status in the Dissemination Activities Registry Google Sheets file (make sure you select the registry table corresponding to the dissemination action you requested approval for e.g. Technical Paper, Mass Media Presence, Project Events).
 - ii. Complete a Dissemination Report and upload it in the Redmine folder Dissemination Reports.
 - iii. The initiator of the dissemination activity is asked to create a sub-folder within Redmine 'Dissemination Activities- Final Submissions' for the corresponding dissemination activity and upload his/her material in it (final version of the i.e paper, presentation, poster etc and any photos). The hyperlink of the subfolder created should be inserted in the dedicated cell in the 'Dissemination Activities Registry' Google Sheet.

Inform the WP9 Leader about the successful completion of the aforementioned steps, by email with subject: "SafePASS – Dissemination Activity Registration".

NOTE:

- If partners wish to present or release material that is already approved as public presentation and material, then no formal approval is required, but the WP9 Leader has to be informed and the event registered in the Dissemination Activities Registry.
- In case a partner wishes to organise a workshop or special event related to SafePASS, then approval by the WP9 Leader is required and the Project Coordinator and Dissemination Board to be informed at least 2 months before the realization of this dissemination activity.

6.2.5 Non- European Travel

For non-European travel the Project Coordinator should be informed and an approval from his side is required. Please fill-in the Non-European Travel Report Template **at least two months** before the travel and send the form to the Project Coordinator so as to inform the EC. Please keep on your record of the form and EC's response along with the respective travel documents for any future enquiries by the auditors.

6.2.6 Acknowledgement on EU funding

According to Article 38 of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement:

Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

- a. Display the EU emblem (when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have **appropriate prominence**)
- b. Include the following text:
 - **For communication activities:** "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 815146. The opinions expressed herein are those of the authors and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains."
 - **For infrastructure, equipment and major results:** "This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 815146."

For correct use of the EC emblem please use the following link:

http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/index_en.htm

For further information please do not hesitate to contact WP9 Leader ([Dr. Evangelos Boulougouris](#), MSRC).

7. Concluding Remarks

The document provided the **Dissemination and Communication Plan** for the SafePASS project. It outlined the strategy for the management and monitoring of the dissemination and communication activities of the project. This strategy will be iteratively updated in line with the needs of the project in order to ensure effectiveness and impact. In this respect, this Plan can be considered a live document, which will be updated periodically. Any changes or deviations from the Plan will be reported in the respective Dissemination and Communication Activity Reports (D9.2.x).

REFERENCES

- [1] SafePASS Consortium and Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA), “Grant Agreement No. 815146- SafePASS,” 2019.
- [2] European Commission, “H2020 Programme- Annotated Model Grant Agreement Version 5.2.” 2019.
- [3] European IPR Helpdesk, “Making the most of your H2020 Project- Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation.” 2018.
- [4] EU- Horizon 2020, “Communicating EU Research and Innovation Guidance for Project Participants.” European Commission, 2014.
- [5] European Commission: Directorate- General for Research and Innovation, “Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020.” 2017.

ANNEXES

Annex 1: SafePASS 1st Press Release – Kick off meeting

The SafePASS project: An EU funded project that is expected to revolutionise emergency response in passenger ships via ‘smart’ devices and novel Life Saving Appliances.

DD/MM/2019, Place

(Name of the company/organisation) is delighted to announce its participation in the eagerly awaited SafePASS project, officially launched in Athens, Greece on 10th and 11th of September 2019. The ambition of this European Commission-funded H2020 project is to bring disruptive change to the marine accident response onboard large passenger ships. SafePASS consortium, coordinated by the National and Technical University of Athens, brings together 15 partners from the industry, academia and classification societies from all over Europe. They all share the vision of making ship evacuation and abandonment safer, faster and smarter. The duration of the project is 3 years extending from September 2019 to August 2022.

Quote from partner and comment on role.

Marine Accidents and Challenges

Marine accidents create the societal pressure for improving safety, but more importantly underpin gaps in our existing procedures, constraints in the capabilities of the existing life-saving appliances and the overall effectiveness of our current procedures and response to the risks posed by the evacuation process itself. The challenge, therefore, lies in the development of cost-effective solutions that will indeed reduce loss of life in case of an evacuation, regardless of the demographical characteristics of the passengers or the environmental conditions at the location of the accident.

To address, adequately, this issue, it is of paramount importance to, learn from experience, pursue international joint research initiatives that can lead to more widely agreed positions in the problem and invest on engineering and research innovations.

EU funding and SafePASS’s inter-disciplinary nature

The EU, appreciating the importance of a system capable of guiding passengers safely in case of an emergency, granted SafePASS approx. 8 million Euros. This funding will be distributed to SafePASS consortium for the purposes of developing ‘deskilled’ and high reliability evacuation systems for passenger ships of large capacities by taking into account social and behavioural aspects as well as extreme weather conditions. The SafePASS system will be tested by developing and implementing pilots and evaluated by quantifiable validation metrics.

Proof of the inter-disciplinary nature and potential of the project can be found in the activities of the partner’s and their leading roles in their areas of expertise. More specifically, the consortium brings together two world-leading LSA manufacturers

(Survitec and Viking), one prominent cruise ship builder (Chantiers de L'Atlantique), one cruise line operator (Royal Caribbean Cruise Line), three EU research institutions (Maritime Safety Research Centre, National Technical University of Athens, Trinity College Dublin), two IACS classification societies (DNVGL, RINA Services & RINA Hellas) and five industrial partners (EXUS Software, Diginext, Crowd Dynamics International, Telesto Technologies, SEAbility).

SafePASS Goal and Objectives

SafePASS system, aims to radically redefine the evacuation processes, evacuation systems and international standards for passenger ships in all environments by developing a combination of innovative systems that will collectively monitor, process and inform during emergencies both safety personnel and passengers of the optimal evacuation routes, coupled with advanced, intuitive and easy to use, lifesaving appliances that go beyond current state-of-the-art. The objectives of the project are summarised below:

- Development of a comprehensive post-incident approach from ALARM to RESCUE, including mustering and abandonment in the corresponding extreme flooding and fire scenarios that will lead to risk estimation and impact of appropriate risk control measures post-flooding/fire emergencies.
- Design and develop the next generation of LSAs for large capacity passenger vessels.
- Design and develop advanced evacuation support tools and methods that will radically improve evacuation operations while enhancing situation awareness on-board.
- Introduce an advanced platform, which addresses the safety needs of passengers during complex evacuation processes by identifying, designating and sustaining a Location-based Dynamic Evacuation Route that adapts according to current and evolving circumstances and guides passengers, while facilitating crew coordination.
- Provide social- and behavioural-driven solutions compatible with international legislation, standards & regulations (SOLAS, GDPR, etc.) and recommendations for future adoption.
- Validate and demonstrate SafePASS developments on industrially relevant environment.

More detailed information will be available in due time through the project's dedicated web site at www.safepass-project.eu .

We are social, don't hesitate to follow or/& contact us:

www.safepass-project.eu

@SafePASS_H2020

info@lists.safepass-project.eu

@company/safepass-project

SafePASS Horizon2020

@SafePASS.H2020

Duration:	1 September 2019 - 31 August 2022 (36 months)
	<i>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. Grant Agreement ID: 815146. Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.</i>
Project Coordinator	Emeritus Prof. Nikolaos Ouzounoglou National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)
Project Manager	Lazaros Karagiannidis National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) Email: lkaragiannidis@esd.ece.ntua.gr , Tel: +30 210 775 4894
Communication Manager	Dr. Evangelos Boulougouris Maritime Safety Research Centre (MSRC), University of Strathclyde Email: evangelos.boulougouris@strath.ac.uk , Tel: +44 (0) 141 548 3875
Partners:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. National Technical University of Athens – Greece 2. EXUS Software Ltd – United Kingdom 3. Maritime Safety Research Centre, University of Strathclyde – United Kingdom 4. Telesto Technologies Information Communication Technologies – Greece 5. Crowd Dynamics International Ltd – United Kingdom 6. Diginext – France 7. Trinity College Dublin – Ireland 8. Survitec Group – United Kingdom 9. Chantiers de l'Atlantique – France 10. RINA Hellas Ltd. – Greece 11. Seability (Cyprus) Ltd – Cyprus 12. Royal Caribbean Cruise Line – United Kingdom 13. DNV GL – Germany 14. RINA Services SPA – Italy 15. VIKING Life Saving Equipment – Denmark
EC funding:	€8,270,366

Annex 2: Dissemination and Communication Opportunities Tables

Table 11: Calendar of Dissemination Opportunity Events

Date	Event	Location	Website	Important Deadlines/ Info
22/04/2020	ICCOE 2020	Singapore	http://www.iccoe.org/	Abstract Deadline 15/12/2019
11/06/2020	ICOE 2020	Osaka, Japan	https://waset.org/ocean-engineering-conference-in-june-2020-in-osaka	Abstract Deadline 01/10/2019
15/01/2020	MD2020	Cadiz, Spain	https://www.rina.org.uk/Marine_Design_2020.html	Abstract Deadline 30/09/2019
04/05/2020	OTC	Houston, Texas, USA	http://2020.otcnet.org/welcome	Abstract Deadline 17/09/2019
14/06/2020	ISOPE	Shanghai, China	https://www.isope.org/	Abstract Deadline 20/10/2019
28/06/2020	OMEA	Fort Lauderdale, USA	https://event.asme.org/OMAE	Abstract Deadline 04/11/2019
08/11/2019	COO	Gdansk, Poland	https://oio.pg.edu.pl/coo/home	Abstract Deadline 30/09/2019
11-12/02/2021	International Conference on Cybersecurity	Barcelona, Spain	https://waset.org/conference/2021/02/Barcelona/ICC	
04-07/05/2021	Transport & Logistic Trade Fair	Exhibition of Munich	https://www.transportlogistic.de/index-2.html	Final Submission 25 January 2021
25-27/02/2020	6th International Conference on Information Systems Security & Privacy	Valleta, Malta	http://www.icissp.org/	
10-13/03/2020	Africa ICS Cybersecurity Conference and Expo 2020	Nairobi, Kenya	https://www.africaicscybersecurityconference.com/	
17-20/03/2020	SITL Transport & Logistics Innovation Week	Paris, France	https://www.sitl.eu/en/home/	
21-23/04/2020	5th Singapore Maritime Technology Conference Exhibition	Marina Bay Sands Singapore	https://www.ibt-asia.com/event/singapore-maritime-technology-conference/	
01-05/06/2020	Posidonia 2020	Athens, Greece, Metropolitan Expo	http://posidonia-events.com/	
09-11/06/2020	TOC Europe	Ahoy Rotterdam, The Netherlands	https://www.tocevents-europe.com/en/Home.html	Participants are served by the Port & Terminal Technology Exhibition which also offers technical seminars, product launches and live demonstrations.
29-03/07/2020	Forum on Integrated and Sustainable Transportation Systems	The Netherlands	https://conferences.ieee.org/conferences_events/conferences/conferencedetails/46898	
04-08/10/2020	ITS World Congress 2020	LA, USA	https://www.itsa.org/new-events/2020/10/4/its-world-congress-2020	

Table 12: List of Scientific Journals for SafePASS papers

No.	Title of Journal	Website	Description

Annex 3: Dissemination Procedures Template Tables

Table 13: Dissemination Activity Request Table

No.	Date of Dissemination Request	Main Leader	Type of Activity	Title of the Event/Journal	Date and Location	URL/website	Title of publication/presentation	Abstract	Authors	Relation to SafePASS	Redmine link to document
0	DD/MM/YYYY	Name, organisation	Please choose one: conference, special session, paper presentation, workshop, demonstration, exhibition, trade fair, press/media activity, poster, video, website, ..., ...							Please choose one: Simple reference, concept description, work description, key paper presenting SafePASS, internal SafePASS activity	

Table 14: Dissemination Activities Registry- Conferences

No.	Date	Lead Partner	Event	Location	Title of Presentation	Involved Partners	Status	Description	Archived Redmine Link	Publication on the website

Table 15: Dissemination Activities Registry- Technical Papers

No.	Title	Authors/ Partners	Event	Date	Status	Published in/DOI	Archived/Redmine Link

Table 16: Dissemination Activities Registry- Journal Papers

No.	Title	Authors/ Partners	Title of Journal	Publication Date/ Publisher	Status	DOI/ Available online at (link(Archived/Redmine Link

Table 17: Dissemination Activities Registry- Project Events

No.	Date	Status	Type of Event	Title	Partners Involved	Description	Redmine Link	Included in the website ?

Table 18: Dissemination Activities Registry- Other Dissemination Activities

No.	Type of Activity	Event	Location/Date	Title of Presentation	Partners involved	Description	Status	Archived/Redmine Link	Included in the website ?

Table 19: Dissemination Activities Registry- Mass Media Presence

No.	Status	Type/Activity	Media Type	Media Name or Link	Title of Publication	Place of Publication	Release Date	Involved partners	Website Link	Brief Description of publication	Archived/Redmine Link
		i.e Press Release	i.e. newspaper, magazine, subject magazine, news portal, subject news portal, subject blog, social media, etc.			i.e. Glasgow, United Kingdom		Please indicate the name of partner who distribute the activity	Please Copy+Paste the publication link (if applicable).	i.e. Press Release republication	Please save the publication in PDF file and archive it in REDMINE. Insert inhere the REDMINE Link.

